

Work Package 8

D8.1-Dissemination and communication strategy M6

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This document describes the dissemination and communication strategy to be adopted by the TALISSMAN project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to appropriate target communities.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
COO	Coordinator
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
LSB	Lithium Sulfur Battery
WPL	Work Package Leader
CA	Consortium Agreement
OA	Open Access
DC	Dissemination and Communication

1. Executive Summary

This document presents the Dissemination and Communication Strategy (D8.1) of the TALISSMAN project, prepared under Task 8.1 and T8.2 and coordinated by SIE. The strategy provides the initial framework for all dissemination and communication activities, ensuring that the project's objectives, progress and results are conveyed clearly and consistently to relevant stakeholders. It sets out the principles, processes and channels that partners will follow to maximise visibility, stimulate knowledge transfer and support exploitation.

The plan is a living document that will be updated at M18, M36 and M48. Each update will report on activities undertaken, evaluate performance against agreed indicators, reflect on lessons learned and adapt methods to further increase impact. This iterative approach ensures that dissemination and communication remain responsive to both project developments and the wider industrial and policy landscape.

The purpose of the strategy is to make TALISSMAN's contributions accessible, credible and relevant. By advancing next-generation lithium-sulphur battery technologies that achieve improvements in performance, safety and cost-effectiveness, the project directly supports European competitiveness and the decarbonisation of transport. Communication and dissemination activities are essential to raising awareness of these achievements, enabling scientific exchange, preparing industrial stakeholders for adoption and fostering trust among policymakers and the public.

Implementation will rely on a balanced mix of channels, including a project website, social media, newsletters, promotional materials, scientific publications, events and targeted engagement. All outputs will follow a unified visual identity and quality standards. In this way, the strategy ensures that TALISSMAN delivers lasting scientific, industrial and societal impact during the project and beyond.

2. Introduction

This deliverable presents the Dissemination and Communication Strategy of the TALISSMAN project. It provides the framework for how SIE and the consortium will present the project to external audiences, share its progress, and promote its results in order to maximise visibility and impact. Prepared under Task 8.1 and Task 8.2 and led by SIE, the document sets out a common approach for all partners and will be updated at M18, M36 and M48 to incorporate the recorded of activities, lessons learned, and improved methods to strengthen outreach and engagement.

The document begins by defining the objectives of the dissemination and communication plan and explaining how these activities contribute to the wider goals of TALISSMAN. It then identifies the project's main target audiences and outlines the key messages that will be adapted to their specific needs. Particular attention is given to ensuring that communication is accessible and tailored, whether addressing researchers, industrial stakeholders, policymakers, or the general public.

A central section of the plan describes the tools and channels that will be used to deliver activities, including the creation of a visual identity, printed and digital materials, the project website, social media, newsletters, press releases, videos, scientific publications, and dedicated workshops and webinars. For each activity, clear indicators are provided to measure performance and ensure accountability.

The plan also introduces the levels of dissemination, the methodology for internal and external communication, and a phased timeline moving from awareness to knowledge transfer and, finally, replication and exploitation. To provide clarity from the outset, the document concludes with a detailed overview of the actions undertaken in the first six months of the project.

3. Objectives of the D&C Plan

The Dissemination and Communication Plan for TALISSMAN has been designed to maximise the visibility and impact of the project's outcomes, while ensuring that knowledge generated is effectively transferred to those stakeholders best positioned to use it. Its primary objective is to guarantee the widespread dissemination of scientific and technological results, ensuring that advances in next-generation lithium–sulphur battery technologies are shared with the research community, industry actors, policymakers, and wider European initiatives. By fostering an open and transparent flow of information, the plan seeks to accelerate knowledge transfer, encourage adoption of innovative solutions, and contribute to the strengthening of European competitiveness in advanced energy storage.

Beyond the scientific and industrial communities, the plan also aims to raise awareness among society at large about the role of publicly funded research in addressing global challenges such as climate change, energy security, and the decarbonisation of transport. By clearly communicating the objectives and expected impacts of TALISSMAN, the strategy intends to increase public understanding of the value of European research and innovation, highlighting how advances in battery technology can deliver both environmental and socio-economic benefits. This societal dimension is essential to ensuring that the project's results are not only recognised by experts, but

also appreciated by the general public as a meaningful contribution to Europe’s sustainability transition.

Another core objective of the plan is to strengthen collaboration between science, industry, and policy. TALISSMAN’s dissemination and communication activities are designed to create opportunities for dialogue and interaction through conferences, workshops, webinars, and networking events. These activities will bring together researchers, manufacturers, policymakers, end-users, and associations to foster knowledge exchange and build durable relationships that outlast the project itself. In doing so, the strategy supports the alignment of scientific advances with market needs and regulatory frameworks, enhancing the potential for successful exploitation and long-term impact.

4. Target audiences & key messages

An effective communication and dissemination strategy begins with a clear identification of the audiences that the project seeks to engage. Each group has specific interests, levels of expertise, and potential roles in supporting the uptake of TALISSMAN’s results. By recognising these differences, the project can tailor its outreach and ensure that information is relevant, accessible, and impactful. Table 1 summarizes the main audiences to reach within the project and the key messages to convey to each of them.

Table 1: Target audiences & Key messages

Target Audience	Purpose	Key Message
Academia and research organisations	Facilitate scientific exchange and replication of results	TALISSMAN generates high-quality knowledge on advanced LSB technologies, shared openly to advance research and innovation.
Active material providers and processors	Encourage collaboration and uptake of component innovations	Project advances in cell components open new market opportunities and increase demand for sustainable, high-performance materials.
Battery manufacturers	Support competitiveness and technology adoption	TALISSMAN strengthens Europe’s battery sector by delivering safer, higher-performing and cost-effective next-generation cells.
End-users (aerospace, aviation, heavy electromobility)	Attract interest in adoption and integration	Project results enable lightweight, safe and efficient batteries tailored for demanding transport applications.

Target Audience	Purpose	Key Message
Sectoral and cross-sectoral associations	Build links to industrial ecosystems and partnerships	TALISSMAN contributes to European competitiveness and supports collective growth of the battery industry.
Policymakers and standardisation bodies	Ensure regulatory alignment and promote standardisation	Project outcomes comply with EU frameworks and provide input to new standards for sustainable batteries.
Society at large	Raise awareness and societal support	TALISSMAN delivers environmental, economic and social benefits, supporting Europe's transition to climate-neutral transport.

These messages must highlight the significance of TALISSMAN's objectives and outcomes, while responding to the priorities of each audience. Delivering targeted, consistent and compelling messages will maximise awareness, foster trust, and encourage active collaboration across science, industry, policy, and society.

5. Tools, channels, and KPIs

This section outlines the methods and platforms that TALISSMAN will employ to disseminate its results, engage stakeholders, and promote its objectives and achievements. It is instrumental in ensuring that the project's outcomes and innovations are effectively communicated to a wide range of audiences, including academic researchers, industry actors, policymakers, sectoral associations, and the general public.

A diverse set of tools and channels has been selected to reach these audiences in ways that are both targeted and complementary. Scientific publications in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals are central to disseminating research findings within academic circles, encouraging knowledge exchange, validation, and collaboration. Dedicated workshops and webinars will provide interactive opportunities for discussion with both the scientific community and policymakers, ensuring real-time feedback and dialogue. In parallel, participation in major international conferences and industrial events will allow TALISSMAN to showcase its progress on a global stage, strengthen cooperation with leading actors in the battery field, and position Europe as a frontrunner in lithium-sulphur battery technology.

Table 2: Dissemination KPIs.

Activity	Target group(s)	KPI
Scientific publications	Academic and scientific community	≥ 12 peer-reviewed open access papers.
Workshops and webinars	Scientific community, policymakers, industry	≥ 4 events organised during the project, with at least 50 participants each.
Conferences and events	Scientific community, industry, sectoral associations	Attend at least 8 conferences per year and present at least 4 per year.
Final project event	Broad stakeholder community	1 large-scale final conference co-organised with EU initiatives.

Digital platforms will play a central role in maintaining continuous engagement. The project website will serve as the hub for all communication activities, providing updated information about objectives, progress, and results. Social media channels, especially LinkedIn, will extend outreach to industry, researchers, and the public, while newsletters will provide regular curated updates to stakeholders across the consortium's networks. Additional communication tools include printed promotional materials, project videos, and press releases, all designed to raise visibility and awareness among non-specialist audiences.

Table 3: Communication KPIs.

Activity	Target group(s)	KPI
Project website	All stakeholders	≥ 800 visitors per year and at least 4 content updates annually; maintained 3 years post-project.
Newsletters	All stakeholders	2 newsletters per year with an average opening rate of ≥ 17%.

Activity	Target group(s)	KPI
Press releases	General public, media	≥ 1 press release per year, targeting at least 100 media outlets/articles covered.
Printed promotional materials	All stakeholders	≥ 100 copies of flyers, roll-ups or leaflets distributed annually.
Social media (LinkedIn)	Scientific community, industry, public	≥ 150 new followers per year and at least 600 impressions annually.
Project videos	All stakeholders	≥ 2 videos produced (introductory at M8 and results-focused at M36) with ≥ 300 views each.

By combining offline and online approaches, TALISSMAN ensures that its communication and dissemination efforts are broad, consistent, and impactful. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), shown in Table 2 and Table 3 for dissemination and communication, respectively, will guide the implementation of the strategy and provide measurable benchmarks for success.

5.1. Project identity

5.1.1. Project Logo

The development of TALISSMAN's visual identity embarked upon a collaborative journey from its inception in the M1 of the project. This task began with the sharing of three distinct logo proposals with the TALISSMAN consortium of partners. The process was led by SIE following an inclusive approach aimed to ensure that all the TALISSMAN consortium partners had a voice in shaping the project's visual representation.

Through a democratic voting process, partners actively participated in selecting the logo that best encapsulated the shared values and objectives of the project. This inclusive decision-making process not only fostered a sense of ownership among partners but also ensured that the chosen logo resonated authentically with the collective vision of

TALISSMAN. Figure 1 shows all the designed logos for TALISSMAN project and the voting results, declaring Option 1 as the winner.

Please select one logo

29 respuestas

Figure 1: TALISSMAN logo voting results.

5.1.2. Brand guidelines and templates

After deciding the project logo, a recognisable project identity was developed to build a visual brand and ultimately offer a package of templates that will facilitate the building of notoriety progressively through the project. This includes creating a project logo and an accompanying style guide. These will be consistently used for the project website and all other communication templates and materials, such as PowerPoint, Word, dissemination materials, and EC reports (see Figure 2).

Brand GuideLines

Color palette

Icon

#E0D015	C 11	#125058	C 88
R 237	M 13	R 18	M 45
G 209	Y 93	G 80	Y 48
B 21	K 0	B 88	K 41

Text

Positive:

#125058	C 88	#333333	C 69
R 18	M 45	R 51	M 60
G 80	Y 48	G 51	Y 56
B 88	K 41	B 51	K 66

Negative:

#000000	C 91	#FFFFFF	
R 0	M 79	R 255	G 255
G 0	Y 62	B 255	B 255
B 0	K 97		

Background graphic elements

#333333	C 69	#F4F4E4	C 6
R 51	M 60	R 244	M 2
G 51	Y 56	G 244	Y 14
B 51	K 66	B 228	K 0

Photo style

Font setting print & desktop presentation

Segoe UI Bold 29 pt

HEADING

#125058

Segoe UI Semibold 25 pt

Subheading

#6FC798

Calibri Regular 22 pt

Subheading 2

#333333

Calibri Light 19 pt

Contents

#333333

Calibri Regular 19pt

Highlight text

#E0D015

Font setting web

Ubuntu Bold 29 pt

HEADING

#125058

Ubuntu Medium 25 pt

Subheading

#6FC798

Lato Regular 19 pt

Subheading 2

#333333

Lato Regular 17 pt

Contents

#333333

Lato Bold 17 pt

Highlight text

#E0D015

Logo color

Iconography

Figure 2: TALISSMAN brand guidelines.

5.1.3. EU Disclaimer

According to Article 17 of the grant agreement, the TALISSMAN project's beneficiaries have already taken into account the legal obligations regarding communication, dissemination, and visibility activities. This includes providing targeted information about the project and its results to multiple audiences in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner. Before engaging in any communication or dissemination activity with significant media impact, beneficiaries informed the granting authority.

Moreover, all communication activities related to the project, such as media relations, conferences, seminars, and information materials, have already acknowledged the support of the European Union and displayed the European flag emblem and funding statement. The European flag emblem has been displayed distinctively and separately, without modification, and no other visual identity or logo has been used to highlight EU support. When displayed alongside other logos, the European emblem has been equally prominent. The European emblem was extracted from [the official EU website](#). Beneficiaries have utilized the European emblem for their obligations under this article without prior approval, in accordance with the grant agreement. However, it is noted that this does not grant them exclusive use rights. Additionally, they have refrained from appropriating the emblem or any similar trademark or logo. All communication and dissemination activities have used factually accurate information to maintain the quality of information provided.

To fulfil these obligations, a disclaimer has been included in all communication materials, stating, ***Funded by the European Union under grant agreement N° 101203047. Views and opinions expressed are however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the CINEA Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This project also contributes to the objectives of the Batt4EU Partnership under call topic ID: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01-05 - Next generation technologies for High-performance and safe-by-design battery systems for transport and mobile applications (Batteries Partnership).*** Additionally, the logo FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION has been prominently displayed in association with other logos (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Example of EU disclaimer application in the TALISSMAN project presentation.

5.2. Printed materials

A poster, a factsheet, a roll-up, a factsheet, project presentation and a brochure have been developed for distribution to partner networks and at conferences, exhibitions, and other events.

These materials are valuable tools for sharing project objectives, achievements, and impacts with various stakeholders, including partners, policymakers, industry professionals, and the general public. By providing comprehensive information in different formats such as brochures, posters, and presentations, the project can enhance visibility, build awareness, and foster engagement, ultimately facilitating collaboration and maximizing the project's overall impact. Table 4 gathers all the printed communication materials and their content.

Table 4: Description of Communication Materials

Material	Description
<u>BROCHURE</u>	This brochure provides an overview of the TALISSMAN project, highlighting its objectives, impacts, and technological innovations. It aims to inform stakeholders about the project's goals and progress. This document also includes information such as project partners' logos, social media links, and the EU disclaimer regarding project funding.
<u>POSTER</u>	The poster presents key information about the TALISSMAN project, including its goals, impacts, and technological innovations. It serves as a visual aid for dissemination and communication activities.
<u>FACTSHEET</u>	The factsheet summarizes essential information about the TALISSMAN project, including its objectives, impacts, and technological innovations. It provides a concise overview for stakeholders.
<u>ROLL UP</u>	The roll-up banner features the project's logo, slogan, partner logos, and social media links. It serves as a promotional tool for

	events and conferences, attracting attention to the TALISSMAN project.
<u>PROJECT PRESENTATION</u>	The project presentation slides provide an overview of the TALISSMAN project, covering its objectives, impacts, technological innovations, methodology, partners, and social media presence.

5.3. Project website

The [TALISSMAN website](#) (see Figure 4) will be the primary source of information for external parties, providing updates on project activities and achievements to all target audiences. The website aims to inform the community and associated industries about project developments, but also to present the project's achievements and novel pilot lines to the public.

All partners will contribute to the website by providing relevant project information. All communication efforts by project partners and social media will always be redirected to the TALISSMAN website. Traffic to the website will be increased by creating mutual links between the partners' websites and other relevant websites and social media channels.

The project website contains:

- [Latest news about the project progress and results.](#)
- [Details about the project partners.](#)
- [Details about related initiatives.](#)
- [Informative materials \(newsletter, materials, articles\).](#)
- [Contact information.](#)
- [Social media links.](#)
- Newsletter subscription in the footer.
- It will include the official project videos (embedded from YouTube) to introduce the main project ambition.
- [Privacy policy](#), [cookies policy](#), and [legal terms](#) to comply with General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) on the protection of natural persons about the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

The project website is set up by SIE and will be managed, maintained, and hosted for the whole duration of the project and the subsequent 3 years after the completion of the project. Statistical data will be collected about the website visitors, which will subsequently be analysed by Google Analytics software and included in the project reports. The website will be responsive to work on a variety of devices and screen sizes, such as smartphones.

WHAT IS THE TALISSMAN PROJECT?

Welcome to the TALISSMAN EU Project – A Horizon Europe research initiative developing sustainable lithium-sulphur batteries for electric mobility. The TALISSMAN EU Project is paving the way for a new generation of batteries that are safer, lighter, and more sustainable. Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme, TALISSMAN focuses on the design and development of advanced lithium-sulphur battery technologies using abundant, low-impact materials like sulphur.

WHY LITHIUM-SULFUR BATTERIES?

Unlike conventional lithium-ion batteries, lithium-sulphur cells have the potential to offer higher energy density, lower costs, and a smaller environmental footprint. Through this innovation, TALISSMAN supports Europe's broader transition to clean energy and transport. The future of batteries should be sustainable, and accessible to all. TALISSMAN is committed to building technologies that serve people, industry, and the planet. [Read more about the importance of sulphur here.](#)

IMPACTS

- Increased Safety:** Solid and quasi-solid electrolytes with strong interface protection reduce fire risk and prevent failures.
- Improved Technical Performance:** TALISSMAN develops batteries with up to 550 Wh/kg, enabling lighter, high-efficiency energy storage for aerospace and electric mobility.
- Superior Cost-Effectiveness:** Using low-cost, abundant materials, TALISSMAN targets <math><€75/kWh</math> by 2030.

Led by CIDETEC Energy Storage, the TALISSMAN EU Project brings together nine leading partners from Spain, France, Germany, and Italy, including Airbus, ARKEMA, Fraunhofer and SAFT. The consortium combines expertise in chemistry, engineering, scale-up, and sustainability, ensuring a multidisciplinary path toward impact. TALISSMAN's innovations are fully aligned with the European Green Deal, the Strategic Action Plan for Batteries, and the Batt4EU partnership. Through a Safe and Sustainable-by-Design approach, the project integrates environmental responsibility, recyclability, and circular economy principles at every step of the development process. We are building batteries that will help Europe move cleaner, faster, and smarter.

NEWS

TALISSMAN EU PROJECT: SULPHUR POWERS BATTERIES

The TALISSMAN EU Project is turning an unlikely material – sulphur – into a key asset for Europe's battery future. While not often in the

[Read More »](#)

SUSTAINABLE LITHIUM-SULPHUR BATTERIES FOR EUROPE'S

In a world moving rapidly towards decarbonisation, sustainable lithium-sulphur batteries are more vital than ever. They are at the heart of electric vehicles.

[Read More »](#)

THE TALISSMAN PROJECT CELEBRATES ITS KICK OFF MEETING IN SAN SEBASTIAN, SPAIN

San Sebastián, Spain – The European-funded TALISSMAN project, aimed at advancing lithium-sulphur battery technologies for sustainable mobility, was officially launched with a two-day kick-off meeting

[Read More »](#)

Figure 4: TALISSMAN website: Home page

5.4. Social Media

The project has a social media presence on [LinkedIn](#) (see Figure 5) to ensure wider dissemination to different age groups and target audiences. Social media will be used as a tool to announce project developments, but most importantly, drive traffic to the project website. LinkedIn has been established, and content related to TALISSMAN has been posted regularly, beginning M1 to increase outreach.

For the first phase of the project, the social media accounts will share posts related to the project scope and post on events where TALISSMAN will be present in order to build a community of interest, creating an audience for sharing project results.

Online media platforms will be monitored to provide information on the analytics, sources, types of content, and individuals/organisations that promote or disseminate project messages, allowing optimisation and targeting of communication to ensure maximum outreach of news or results. These results will also be included in interim reports and the final dissemination report. The social media accounts will be managed by SIE with support from the partners.

Consortium partners are following the project's social media channels and engage with them as much as possible. Whenever possible, the partners will share posts on their corporate websites and social media networks. If they need assistance, SIE can guide them on the best ways to do so.

Figure 5: TALISSMAN LinkedIn profile.

5.5. Press Releases and Newsletters

Press releases and newsletters are essential tools within the TALISSMAN communication strategy, ensuring both regular visibility and structured outreach to diverse stakeholders. They complement other digital channels such as the website and social media by providing curated, timely and accessible information about the project's progress, achievements and events.

Press releases will be issued at key milestones of the project to capture the attention of media outlets, industry magazines and wider audiences. These releases will highlight significant developments such as the launch of the project, major scientific or technical breakthroughs, participation in high-level events, and the final results. By delivering concise, news-oriented messages, the press releases will raise awareness of TALISSMAN beyond the immediate research and industrial community, positioning the project within the broader European debate on battery innovation, sustainable transport and climate neutrality. To maximise coverage, they will be circulated through consortium networks and targeted to relevant media channels.

Newsletters, on the other hand, will serve as a regular communication vehicle to maintain engagement with stakeholders throughout the project. Issued twice per year, they will include updates on project activities, interviews with partners, upcoming events, scientific highlights and dissemination opportunities. The newsletters will be distributed electronically through partner mailing lists, uploaded to the website, and promoted on social media. Their objective is to keep the project's community informed and to ensure that stakeholders remain connected to TALISSMAN's progress over time.

Together, press releases and newsletters provide a structured yet flexible means of maintaining visibility, strengthening stakeholder relationships and ensuring that the project's messages reach both specialised and general audiences in a consistent and accessible format.

5.6. Project videos

Project videos will play a central role in TALISSMAN's communication activities by providing engaging, accessible, and visually appealing content to a wide range of stakeholders. They complement more traditional written outputs such as newsletters, press releases and scientific publications, offering a dynamic way to present the project's objectives and results in a concise and memorable format.

Two videos are foreseen during the project. The first, to be released around Month 8, will serve as an introductory piece. It will present TALISSMAN's vision, main objectives, expected impacts, and the role of the consortium partners. Designed to be clear and accessible for non-specialist audiences, this video will help build awareness, foster early engagement, and create a sense of identity and visibility for the project during its initial phase. It will be hosted on the project website, promoted through social media, and shared at relevant events. The second video, scheduled for release around Month 36, will focus on showcasing TALISSMAN's progress, key achievements, and final results. It will highlight technological advances, scientific insights, and potential applications, placing particular emphasis on the benefits for industry, policymakers, and society at large. This video will act as a legacy tool, ensuring that the project's contributions remain accessible and understandable even after its formal conclusion.

Both videos will be produced in a professional style, aligned with the project's visual identity, and subtitled to increase accessibility. Together, they will provide an effective means of engaging audiences, enhancing outreach, and ensuring that TALISSMAN's messages are communicated in a clear and impactful manner.

5.7. Scientific Publications

Scientific publications represent one of the most important dissemination tools of the TALISSMAN project, ensuring that new knowledge generated is rigorously validated, openly accessible, and widely shared within the research community. They serve as a bridge between the project's technical advances and the wider academic and industrial ecosystems, enabling replication, comparison, and the development of follow-up research activities. Partners are committed to producing at least twelve peer-reviewed publications in high-impact, open-access journals throughout the duration of the project. These journals are expected to include leading titles in the fields of electrochemistry, materials science, and energy research. Open access will guarantee that results are available to the global scientific community, in line with Horizon Europe requirements and the project's commitment to transparency. Publications will cover a range of topics, from fundamental materials characterisation and cell design innovations to process optimisation and sustainability assessments. They will not only validate the scientific credibility of TALISSMAN's findings but also contribute to positioning Europe at the forefront of next-generation battery research. In addition, publications will provide opportunities for academic and industrial collaboration, feeding into conferences, workshops, and wider policy dialogues.

5.8. Workshops and webinars

Workshops and webinars will provide TALISSMAN with interactive platforms to engage directly with its key audiences, facilitating dialogue, knowledge exchange, and collaboration. They are therefore essential instruments for strengthening the link between science, industry, policymakers, and wider society. At least four workshops or webinars will be organised during the project, primarily in the second half when tangible results begin to emerge. These events will be coordinated by SIE with the support of all partners and will be designed to maximise accessibility through hybrid or fully online formats. Each workshop will focus on a specific theme, such as materials innovation, manufacturing processes, safety validation, or sustainability assessment, ensuring that the content is both relevant and timely for participants. By doing so, TALISSMAN will create opportunities to demonstrate progress, gather expert input, and expand its network of stakeholders. Attendance targets will aim for a minimum of 50 participants per event, bringing together researchers, industry representatives, policymakers, and sectoral associations. Beyond knowledge transfer, the workshops and webinars will also act as recruitment channels for new stakeholders interested in contributing to the project's objectives or exploring future collaborations. All events will be promoted through the project's website, social media, newsletters, and partner networks, while summaries and recordings will be made available afterwards to ensure broader dissemination.

5.9. Clustering with EU initiatives

Clustering with European initiatives and related projects is a key element of TALISSMAN's dissemination and communication strategy. By aligning with established platforms and partnerships, the project can ensure that its results contribute to wider European objectives while benefitting from enhanced visibility, collaboration opportunities, and knowledge exchange.

TALISSMAN will actively seek synergies with the Batteries European Partnership Association (BEPA) and Battery 2030+, the two main initiatives driving forward Europe's long-term research and innovation agenda in advanced battery technologies. Engagement with these platforms will facilitate the integration of TALISSMAN's findings into broader roadmaps, policy discussions, and industrial strategies, ensuring that the project's contributions reach decision-makers at the European level.

In addition, the project will prioritise cooperation with other Horizon Europe projects funded under the same call topic. In particular, TALISSMAN will develop links with the ANGeLiC Project and the HighMag Project, establishing opportunities for joint events,

co-organised workshops, and the exchange of technical insights. These collaborations will create a stronger collective impact, reduce duplication of efforts, and promote a coherent European approach to next-generation battery development.

5.10. Conferences & Events

Participation in conferences and events forms a central pillar of TALISSMAN's dissemination and communication strategy. These activities enable the consortium to present achievements, exchange knowledge, engage stakeholders, and position the project within the wider European and international battery landscape. Unlike one-way communication tools, conferences provide interactive spaces that allow feedback, dialogue, and collaboration, reinforcing both the visibility and credibility of the project.

TALISSMAN will be present at a variety of events, including scientific conferences, industrial fairs, and European policy platforms. On the scientific side, international meetings such as the International Conference on Li-Sulfur Batteries, Electrochemical Society (ECS) gatherings, and International Society of Electrochemistry (ISE) conferences will serve as primary venues to disseminate research results, validate findings, and connect with global research leaders. Industrial events such as The Battery Show Europe and Battery Innovation Days will target manufacturers, suppliers, and end-users, providing opportunities to demonstrate the relevance of TALISSMAN's results for aerospace, aviation, and heavy electromobility sectors.

At the European level, the consortium will actively engage with BEPA, Battery 2030+ and the Batt4EU Partnership, ensuring alignment with broader research agendas and policy dialogues. Clustering activities with sister projects funded under the same topic, notably ANGeLiC and HighMag, will be pursued through joint events and co-organised sessions, maximising synergies and strengthening collective impact.

The strategy also foresees the organisation of a final high-level conference towards the end of the project. This event will gather researchers, industry actors, policymakers and associations to showcase TALISSMAN's achievements, highlight exploitation opportunities, and explore future pathways to market.

Overall, conferences and events provide TALISSMAN with powerful opportunities to ensure that its results reach the scientific community, industry stakeholders, and policymakers, thereby supporting their long-term exploitation and reinforcing Europe's leadership in advanced battery technologies.

6. Levels of dissemination

6.1. European Level – European Commission

The European Commission will be informed about the results via the periodic reporting of the project (mid-term review, minutes of periodical meetings, updates of this document) in order to modify related regulations if necessary and to propose collaboration with other ongoing projects on dissemination activities.

6.2. International Level – Stakeholders

The relevant international and national organisations will be informed of the results. Scientific knowledge can be translated into practical information, guidelines, and regulatory policies. Direct mailing to specific organisations and stakeholders will be used to distribute electronic resources to raise public awareness. Technical journals, conferences and workshops at both national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be used for the dissemination of knowledge both at research and industrial levels.

7. Methodology

The following internal and external communication activities will be undertaken during the project's lifetime and afterward to ensure that the results of TALISSMAN are efficiently and effectively communicated to the project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

7.1. Internal communication

Effective internal communication is key to sharing information and ensuring that the deliverables are met. Therefore, annual face-to-face meetings and conference calls will take place to exchange project information, update progress, and share results. Consortium and technical meetings will take place at least one time a year, while Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing services will be used to facilitate collaboration within WPs.

Apart from specific emails, taking advantage of the at least one yearly general assembly, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination

Plan and streamline a content curation process. This will allow the partners to take a more focused and systematic approach, strengthening actions taken to communicate and report on the project. A delegate from all consortium partners of TALISSMAN will attend this meeting.

7.2. External communication

All efforts will be made to publish the work of the consortium via the media, publications, conference presentations, trade fairs, and workshops, as well as through the Commission and industry bodies. Results of the project will be disseminated via reports, scientific papers, and technical articles. All public communication, and in particular scientific publications, will be made open access, to facilitate scientific exchange.

All project partners are expected to support dissemination since all beneficiaries have allocated a budget for D&C activities, to ensure that stakeholders will be engaged throughout the lifetime of the project. Partners' activities may include but are not limited to: engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based), contributing to SIE's inputs on social media, proactively sharing information with SIE about project results, listing their communication activities in a shared file, and providing SIE with translations of lay materials in their local language. Where possible, partners will translate press releases into their national languages and keep SIE informed about plans, by creating lists of national media channels they will try to reach.

8. Timeline

The dissemination and communication strategy of TALISSMAN has been designed as an evolving framework that adapts to the project's progress and maturity. Activities are structured across three main phases, each corresponding to different stages in the research lifecycle and tailored to the needs of the target audiences. This phased approach ensures that communication efforts remain timely, relevant, and impactful, while steadily building awareness, engagement, and readiness for exploitation.

8.1. Community Building (M1-M12)

The first phase, Community Building (M1–M12), focuses on establishing the project's communication channels and creating visibility around its objectives and expected outcomes. During this period, the project website, social media accounts, newsletters and visual identity will be launched. Key messages will centre on introducing TALISSMAN's aims, presenting the consortium partners, and building an initial network

of stakeholders. This early visibility is essential for creating momentum and trust, laying the groundwork for effective dissemination later in the project.

8.2. R&D Diffusion & Cooperation (M12-M36)

The second phase, R&D Diffusion and Cooperation (M12–M36), begins once results start to emerge. Dissemination activities will intensify, with outputs such as scientific publications, conference presentations, workshops and webinars enabling active knowledge transfer and stakeholder feedback. Communication to the general public will highlight project achievements in accessible language, ensuring that scientific progress is translated into clear societal benefits. This phase plays a critical role in fostering dialogue between researchers, industry, policymakers and citizens, creating a shared sense of ownership and interest in TALISSMAN’s innovations.

8.3. Exploitation Enablement (M24-M48)

The final phase, Exploitation Enablement (M24–M48), is designed to prepare the ground for the uptake of results. Dissemination will increasingly target industry, sectoral associations and policymakers to reinforce the visibility of exploitable results and to facilitate their integration into market and regulatory frameworks. Activities will include intensified engagement with industrial stakeholders, clustering with EU initiatives, and the organisation of the project’s final event to showcase achievements and demonstrate their potential applications.

9. Actions M1-M6

9.1. Project Identity and materials

As described in the previous sections, a visual identity for TALISSMAN was created. It included the logo of the project, and the brand guidelines (typography, colours, iconography, photography style) as well as different communication materials, including a brochure, a roll-up, a poster, and a project presentation and templates in Word and PowerPoint.

The brochure, poster, factsheet, roll-up, and project presentation were produced and made available on the website of the project as soon as it was operative (see Figure 6):

<https://talissman.eu/documents/>

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Figure 6: Communication materials on the TALISSMAN website.

9.2. Project website

The [TALISSMAN](#) website was launched in the first month of the project with essential information about the project that will be updated constantly with progress and news from the project and partners.

Since the website has been operational until mid-November, it has accounted for 879 visits, reaching the yearly KPI established in the previous sections. These numbers are very good and indicate that the project is getting very qualified website traffic. Figure 7 shows the web audience overview for the period concerned between 1st July and 17th November 2025.

Figure 7: Google Analytics from July to December

The news section has been updated with relevant information about the project:

- [TALISSMAN EU PROJECT: SULPHUR POWERS BATTERIES](#)
- [SUSTAINABLE LITHIUM-SULPHUR-BATTERIES FOR EUROPE'S](#)
- [THE TALISSMAN PROJECT CELEBRATES ITS KICK OFF MEETING IN SAN SEBASTIAN, SPAIN](#)
- [THE TALISSMAN PROJECT WEBSITE IS LIVE](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH J. ALBERTO BLÁZQUEZ – CIDETEC ENERGY STORAGE](#)
- [TALISSMAN AT THE 12TH LITHIUM-SULFUR BATTERIES WORKSHOP](#)
- [TALISSMAN PRESENTED AT GENERA 2025 IN MADRID](#)
- [CIDETEC ENERGY STORAGE ATTENDS THE BATTERY INNOVATION DAYS](#)

9.3. Social Media

The official project channels were launched in Month 1, with the first post dedicated to sharing the official [press release announcing the start of TALISSMAN and highlighting the Kick-Off Meeting](#) (see Figure 9). This marked the first public milestone of the project and served as the foundation for subsequent communication efforts. To ensure wide reach and consistent partner engagement, all consortium members have been tagged in every post published. This approach has helped amplify visibility across the networks of individual partners, reinforcing the sense of joint ownership and maximising the dissemination of messages. Updates have been published at least once per week, providing a steady flow of content and maintaining regular interaction with stakeholders. During the first six months, the focus of content has been on explaining [TALISSMAN's objectives](#), [expected impacts](#), methodological approach, and the role of the consortium partners. Posts have also been used to share communication materials, including visual assets aligned with the project's brand identity. This content strategy has ensured that the foundations of the project are well understood by both specialist and non-specialist audiences, creating a strong narrative to accompany its technical progress. The results of these efforts are already visible. TALISSMAN's LinkedIn account has gained more than 200 followers in its first six months and more than 11,000 impressions, with an average rate of engagement rate of 17,2% reflecting strong interest in the project and a growing community of stakeholders committed to following its development (see Figure 8). This positive engagement demonstrates the relevance of the project's objectives and the effectiveness of the social media strategy implemented to date.

Figure 8: LinkedIn audience overview.

Figure 9: Example of Social Media Post.

9.4. Newsletters and press releases

During the first six months of TALISSMAN, newsletters and press releases have been key instruments to formally present the project to stakeholders and the wider public. The [first project newsletter](#) was released in M6 (December 2025) and distributed to a contact list built throughout the first semester. More than 100 relevant contacts were collected during this period, including representatives from research organisations, industry, associations, and policy bodies. The newsletter introduced TALISSMAN's objectives, methodology, expected impacts, consortium partners, and the outcomes of the Kick-Off Meeting. It also highlighted the launch of the official project website, creating an integrated message that reinforced the identity and purpose of the project from the outset.

With regard to press releases, the official TALISSMAN press release was launched on 10 July 2025, coinciding with the project’s start and the Kick-Off Meeting. It was disseminated to more than 200 media outlets and translated into Spanish in recognition of the strong representation of Spanish partners in the consortium, including CIDETEC, SIE, TECNALIA, and AIRBUS. The press release was widely circulated by all partners through their own channels, further amplifying its reach and ensuring strong visibility across both national and European audiences. The media response was positive, with numerous articles and mentions published in specialised and general press outlets. A detailed overview of these media impacts is presented in Table 5:

Table 5: Impacts in media

MEDIA	LINK
EE NEWS	https://www.ee-news.ch/de/article/56033/justus-liebig-universitat-giessen-talissman-entwickelt-batterien-der-funften-generation
GIESSENER-ANZEIGER	https://www.giessener-anzeiger.de/stadt-giessen/batterien-der-fuenften-generation-93673547.html
MUNDO RECAMBIO	https://mundorecambio.info/espana-impulsa-innovacion-baterias-litio-azufre-movilidad-sostenible-europa/
OPEN PR	https://www.openpr.com/news/4099156/talissman-the-project-that-seeks-to-develop-safer-more
QUIMICA ES	https://www.quimica.es/noticias/1185937/la-quinta-generacion-de-pilas.html
WIT NEWS	https://witnews.eu/talissman-advanced-li-s-batteries-for-e-mobility/

Figure 10: Impacts on Media Outlets

Together, the launch of the first newsletter and the dissemination of the official press release provided a strong foundation for TALISSMAN’s external communication, helping to establish awareness, generate interest and build credibility during the crucial first months of the project.

9.5. Clustering with EU initiatives

During the first six months of the project, TALISSMAN has taken important steps to establish its clustering activities and strengthen connections with related European initiatives. A mapping exercise was carried out to identify the most relevant projects and

platforms with which synergies can be created. This analysis highlighted two Horizon Europe projects funded under the same topic, ANGeLiC and HighMag, as well as the large-scale initiatives BEPA and Battery 2030+, which play a leading role in shaping Europe's battery research and innovation agenda.

Following this identification, SIE has created a [dedicated section on the TALISSMAN website](#) to showcase these initiatives. Each entry includes a short description and a direct link to the corresponding project or platform, providing visibility for related activities while positioning TALISSMAN as an active contributor to the European battery ecosystem.

In addition to this mapping and online integration, TALISSMAN has already initiated contact with the communication managers of ANGeLiC and HighMag to explore practical collaboration opportunities. A concrete proposal has been made to implement cross-follow activities on social media, including mutual tagging in posts and coordinated sharing of updates. This approach will maximise the visibility of each project, strengthen their combined outreach, and demonstrate the coherence of European efforts in advancing next-generation battery technologies.

These initial clustering actions provide a strong foundation for more ambitious joint activities in later phases of the project, including co-organised workshops and joint contributions to European-level platforms. They reflect TALISSMAN's commitment to cooperation, visibility, and long-term impact within the European research and innovation landscape.

9.6. Conferences & Events

During the first six months of the project, SIE has actively monitored partner participation in conferences and events through the use of dissemination tables. This system allows the consortium to collect detailed information on dissemination and communication activities, ensuring centralised tracking and reporting. Partners are requested to provide the title, date, description, and an accompanying image for each event they attend. Once received, SIE compiles and validates this information and publishes it on the project website, thereby ensuring that all activities are consistently documented and made visible to external audiences.

As regards participation in external events during this period, SIE represented TALISSMAN at [GENERA 2025](#), held in Madrid in November. This event, one of Spain's key energy and sustainability fairs, provided an excellent opportunity to establish new contacts, expand the project's professional network, and present its objectives to a broad audience including industry stakeholders, researchers and policymakers. The presence of TALISSMAN at GENERA marked an important first step in the project's

engagement with the wider innovation community, supporting early visibility and reinforcing its position within the European battery ecosystem.

Figure 11: SIE attending the GENERA trade fair

On 17–18 November 2025, the TALISSMAN project took part in the 12th “[Lithium–Sulfur Batteries](#)” Workshop, organised by Fraunhofer IWS in Dresden. Our coordinator, Alberto Blázquez (CIDETEC Energy Storage) (see Figure 12), presented the project during the poster session, sharing insights into TALISSMAN’s vision for next-generation Gen5 Li–S batteries. Throughout the event, the team distributed the official project flyers and engaged with researchers and industry stakeholders.

Figure 12: CID and Fraunhofer IWS in the Lithium-Sulfur Batteries Workshop

On December 2–3, 2025, [Battery Innovation Days 2025 \(BID 2025\)](#) gathered leading European stakeholders in battery research, industry, policy and innovation and the TALISSMAN project was present through the active participation of our coordinator CIDETEC Energy Storage (see Figure 13). The event, held in Graz (Austria) provided a unique platform for presenting cutting-edge battery EU initiatives under the auspices of Battery 2030+ and Batteries European Partnership Association (BEPA).

Figure 13: CIDETEC Energy Storage in the Battery Innovations Days 2025

Through these initial activities, the project has laid the groundwork for a more extensive presence in upcoming conferences and events. The established monitoring process ensures that all partner contributions are captured, reported and disseminated, while early participation has already demonstrated the value of direct engagement with stakeholders in promoting TALISSMAN’s goals.

10. Annexes

10.1. BROCHURE

PROJECT PARTNERS

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TALISSMAN

Technologies for Advanced Lithium-Sulphur batteries toward Safe and Sustainable Mobility Applications.

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement N° 101203047. Views and opinions expressed are however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the CINEA Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

ABOUT TALISSMAN

TALISSMAN (Technologies for Advanced Lithium-Sulphur batteries toward Safe and Sustainable Mobility Applications) is a Horizon Europe project which seeks to develop safe, high-performance, and sustainable lithium-sulphur batteries for aerospace and electromobility applications. By advancing gelled and solid-state battery concepts, TALISSMAN addresses key technical barriers to industrialisation. The project integrates eco-design, circularity, and recyclability principles, while ensuring compatibility with existing production lines.

THE 7 OBJECTIVES

To achieve its vision of next-generation, safe and sustainable lithium-sulphur batteries, TALISSMAN sets out seven strategic objectives that span material innovation, cell design, manufacturing, sustainability, and industrial uptake.

- Safe and efficient 3D lithium-metal anodes
- Advanced electrolytes for stable performance
- High-performance sulphur cathodes
- Understanding and preventing battery degradation process
- Pilot-scale validation of battery prototypes
- Sustainability and circularity by design
- Industrial uptake and exploitation

IMPACTS

Improved Technical Performance:
TALISSMAN will deliver next-gen batteries with energy densities up to 550 Wh/kg (watt-hours per kilogram), meaning more energy stored with less weight – a key enabler for high-efficiency aerospace and electric mobility applications.

Increased Safety:
By replacing flammable liquid electrolytes with quasi-solid and solid-state alternatives, and implementing robust interface protection, TALISSMAN significantly lowers the risk of thermal runaway and dendrite-induced failures.

Superior Cost-Effectiveness:
Thanks to low-cost, abundant materials like sulphur and carbon, combined with scalable, energy-dense designs, TALISSMAN aims to reduce battery costs below €75/kWh by 2030, enhancing competitiveness against conventional LIBs.

METHODOLOGY

WPI: Project Management

WPI-1: Lithium/3D Lithium Metal Anode Development | WPI-2: Advanced Electrolyte and Separator Development | WPI-3: High-Performance Sulphur Cathode Development

WPI-4: Cell Development and Prototype Manufacturing

WPI-5: Cell Prototype Assessment, Degradation Mechanisms and Modelling

WPI-6: DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION

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10.2. ROLL-UP

TALISSMAN
Technologies for Advanced Lithium-Sulphur batteries toward Safe and Sustainable Mobility Applications.

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10.3. PROJECT PRESENTATION

The presentation consists of six slides:

- Slide 1:** TALISSMAN Technologies for Advanced Lithium-Sulfur batteries toward Safe and Sustainable Mobility Applications.
- Slide 2:** TALISSMAN is a Horizon Europe project which seeks to develop safe, high-performance, and sustainable lithium-sulfur batteries for aerospace and electromobility applications. By advancing gel-free and solid-state battery concepts, TALISSMAN addresses key technical barriers to industrialization. The project integrates eco-design, circularity, and recyclability principles, while ensuring compatibility with existing production lines. A strong focus on stakeholder engagement and open science will support tracker update and contribute to Europe's battery technology leadership.
- Slide 3:** IMPACTS and OBJECTIVES. IMPACTS include Improved Technical Performance (increasing energy density to 350 Wh/kg), Increased Safety (reducing thermal runaway risk), and Superior Cost-Effectiveness (reducing material costs). OBJECTIVES include Safe and efficient Li-S battery systems, High performance sulfur cathodes, Understanding and governing battery degradation physics, Pilot scale validation of battery prototypes, Sustainability and circularity by design, and Industrial uptake and exploitation.
- Slide 4:** METHODOLOGY. WPI: Project Management. WPI: Lightweight Li-S Batteries, WPI: Advanced Electrolyte and Separator Development, WPI: Sulfur Composite Cathode Development. WPI: Cell Development and Prototype Manufacturing. WPI: Cell Electrolyte Assessment, Key-Parameter Assessment and Production. WPI-9: DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION.
- Slide 5:** PROJECT PARTNERS. Includes logos for cidetec, AIRBUS, ARHE/AAA, Fraunhofer, and tecnalia. Lists countries: SPAIN, FRANCE, GERMANY, ITALY.
- Slide 6:** TALISSMAN TALISSMAN PROJECT www.talissman.eu

10.4. POSTER

TALISSMAN

Technologies for Advanced Lithium-Sulfur batteries toward Safe and Sustainable Mobility Applications.

TALISSMAN

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The project integrates eco-design, circularity, and recyclability principles, while ensuring compatibility with existing production lines.

IMPACTS

Improved Technical Performance

TALISSMAN will deliver next-gen batteries with energy densities up to 350 Wh/kg (wet-hours per kilogram), meaning more energy stored with less weight – a key enabler for high-efficiency aerospace and electric mobility applications.

Increased Safety

By replacing flammable liquid electrolytes with quasi-solid and solid-state alternatives, and implementing robust interface protection, TALISSMAN significantly lowers the risk of thermal runaway and dendrite-induced failures.

Superior Cost-Effectiveness

Thanks to low-cost, abundant materials like sulfur and carbon, combined with scalable, energy-dense designs, TALISSMAN aims to reduce battery costs below €100/kWh by 2030, enhancing competitiveness against conventional LIBs.

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10.5. FACTSHEET

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The project integrates eco-design, circularity, and recyclability principles, while ensuring compatibility with existing production lines.

● 9 Project Partners
from 4 EU countries

● €4.9 million
in EU funding

● 48-month project
duration (2025–2029)

● 2 battery types: hybrid
and solid-state

● Energy storage: up to 550
hours per kilogram

● Power output: up to
3300 watts per kilogram

● Battery life: up to
700 full charge cycles

● Cost goal: under €75 per
kilowatt-hour by 2030

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